

Smart Security System

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Abstract— the present security system takes longer time for sending security alerts. It's reported that they are system which sends the alert message after a duration of the occurrence of security violation. This paper mainly focuses on development of system which works rapidly for short time period. The security is important to provide safety, therefore, a smart security system is being proposed in this paper which monitor and alert regarding the un-usual activities. This security system plays a vital role in securing the location. This remote security system which is used for detection of harmful gases or smoke, detection of fire, detection of theft, etc. It has been successfully completed, and this system send the notification to the owner's mobile phone regarding the problems in form of SMS alerts. This system also has an exhaust fan which works automatically when there is presence of harmful smoke or gas. The security system programmed in the Embedded C programming. The system is wireless therefore adaptable and greater efficiency. In this project we have developed an economically smart security system with fault-tolerant, secured, easy to install and use surveillance system through wireless connection using lower cost devices controlled by smart phones

Index Terms—Smart Security System, Remote Security, SMS alerts, short time period, Embedded C Programming.

I. INTRODUCTION

The wireless security system is essential for prevention of unauthorized access and secure using the Mobile with the usage of wireless networks. This project mainly focuses on security alert systems. We have developed a system for controlling and monitoring of home appliances remotely and providing security that is Remote Home security alarm system using the GSM, Gas sensors, Fire sensor, LDR and PIR sensors.

Remote Home security alarm system using GSM module, Fire sensor, smoke or gas sensors, LDR module and PIR sensors in this system it mainly focuses on the controlling and monitoring of home appliances remotely and providing security. In this system, a GSM module is used to continuously monitor the output. For any application in the home there are many parameters to be handled. Here, we are concentrating on intruder, smoke sensor, gas (LPG) sensor and fire sensor. These sensors are fixed at specified location in home, for our system to function. The Sensor gathers the values and sends the information to the microcontroller continuously. The microcontroller which is AT89S25 receives the values and sends the corresponding values to the LCD to display. It is a cyclic process which performs continuously. Whenever the smoke exceeds the limit set point the controller will send the SMS to the owner's number and it switch on the exhaust fan. When the fire is detected by fire sensor, the controller will send the SMS to owner's number and display in the LCD. Whenever the gas is detected, the controller will send the SMS to the owner's number and it switch on the exhaust fan and gives the alarm. A part of this system is also installed in the main door, if in case any person other than owner enters into the home the sensor will identify and send the SMS to the particular number.

II. RESEARCH STUDIES

[1]. This research describes a low cost and flexible security system which is basically based on Arduino with necessary interface to enable Internet and the control of power through Global System for Mobile Communication (GSM) & Bluetooth module (HC-05). This paper consumed more real life interactions along with embedded software solutions. In this project a password is set for the access of all sensors, for this we use LCD Display and Keypad. Motion sensor, gas module, reed sensor, laser sensor, all the sensors are used to detect theft and unwanted occurrences. Control Panel Interface of Web Server and android voice control both are created to control of all lights of the organization and for the purpose of power savings. The main contribution of this paper is that it not only helps to ensure the security of an organization but also energy efficient and time saving.

[2]. The aim of this paper is to investigate a cost effective solution that will provide controlling of home appliances remotely and will also enable home security against intrusion in the absence of home owner. The proposed system characteristics involve remote controlling of appliances, intrusion detection, system security and auto-configuration such that system automatically adjusts the system settings on running hardware support check. The system uses latest wireless communication like Bluetooth, Infrared and Wi-Fi access to the system for security and automated appliance control. Capturing images and sound recording will be able to display at remote places.

[3]. This paper explains about the current status and analysis of Internet of things (IoT) security. IoT structure pursue to append anyone with anything, anywhere. An IoT normally has a three imaginary layers consisting of realization, Network, and Application layers. This paper narrates security problems within and across these layers. Many security ideas that should be implemented at each layer are also furnished. The IoT framework is vulnerable to attacks at each layer. Therefore, there are many security threats and requirements that need to be dispatched. Current state of research in IoT is mainly concentrated on

authentication and access control protocols, but with the rapid growth of technology it is essential to consolidate new networking protocols like Ipv6 and 5G to achieve the progressive mash up of IoT topology. The major developments supported in IoT are mainly on small scale including within companies and in some limited industries

[4]. This paper gives the glimpse on solution by power cut the gas provision as soon as a gas leakage is perceived apart from activating the sounding alarm. In addition to this, the authorized person will receive a message informing him about the leakage. This system will help a lot in terms of preventing any danger caused by gas leakage and useful as part of safety to avoid the gas leak that can cause harmful result. It will also improve the safety of all users of Liquefied Petroleum Gas. This project uses various components like Arduino Uno, Gsm module and sensors. The main aim of this project is as soon as the smoke sensor detects the harmful gas, it will cut of the LPG supply to application and send a sound alarm and sms alert using the Gsm module to authorized person.

III. DESIGN

Fig1. Block Diagram

Fig2. Regulated Power supply

Fig3. Circuit diagram in Express PCB

Some of the major components used in the project are:

1. **AT89525 Microcontroller-** The AT89C52 is a low-power, high-performance CMOS 8-bit microcomputer with 8Kbytes of Flash programmable and erasable read only memory (PEROM). The on-chip Flash allows the program memory to be reprogrammed in-system or by a conventional non-volatile memory programmer. By combining a versatile 8-bit CPU with Flash on a monolithic chip, the Atmel AT89C52 is a powerful microcomputer, which provides a highly flexible and cost-effective solution to many embedded control applications.
2. **GSM Module-** A GSM modem is a specialized type of modem which accepts a SIM card, and operates over a subscription to a mobile operator, like a mobile phone. From the mobile operator perspective, a GSM modem is a mobile phone. While these GSM modems are most frequently used to provide mobile internet connectivity, many of them can also be used for sending and receiving SMS and MMS messages. A GSM modem can be a dedicated modem device with a serial, USB or Bluetooth connection, or it can be a mobile phone that provides GSM modem capabilities.
3. **MAX-32-** The Max32 is a microcontroller board based on the Microchip PIC32MX795F512L, a member of the 32-bit PIC32 microcontroller family.

- LDR Module-** Photoresistors, also known as light dependent resistors (LDR), are light sensitive devices most often used to indicate the presence or absence of light, or to measure the light intensity.
- Sensor-** There are different sensors used under this project they are gas or smoke sensor, fire sensors and PIR sensor. gas or smoke sensor is used to detect presence of any harmful gas or smoke in the location. PIR sensor used to detect the motion. Fire sensor is used to detect the presence of any fire in the particular location.

IV. CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

The circuit diagram of this project is planned and designed in the Express PCB software and programmed using the Embedded C programming. The program was written and tested in the Kiel software. In this project At89S25 microcontroller is used which is the heart of the project. This project has components attached to the microcontroller. In this circuit diagram we have used, MAX232 which is a dual transmitter/dual receiver which is used for serial communication with GSM module. In this project we have designed a power supply unit which is used to get 5V DC voltage. An adapter is used to provide the external power supply to the project. When external power supply is given to the project, the LCD will display "Remote Home security system". When the sensors senses the input it will send the signal to the microcontroller to perform particular function. When the PIR sensor, which is installed in door detects the motion, it will send the alert to the GSM module to send SMS alert to owner mobile phone and it will display the alert message in LCD. When the Gas sensor detects any harmful gas or any smoke it will send alert to the GSM module to send SMS alert to owner mobile phone and it will display the alert message in LCD. Also it will start running of the exhaust fan and send an alarm sound using buzzer. When the fire sensor detects the fire it will send alert to the GSM module to send SMS alert to owner mobile phone and it will display the alert message in LCD. There is also a LDR module when it detects any flash light it will send an alert.

V. REGULATED POWER SUPPLY

The power supply unit is used to provide constant 5 V dc supply to the peripherals. The 230 V ac is converted into 9 V ac by using a transformer and then a bridge rectifier rectifies it to a 9 V dc with ac ripples. This is then filtered by electrolytic capacitors used across the rectifier output. LM7805 regulator is employed to obtain a constant 5 V dc at the output.

Features of the Regulated power supply:

- Circuit complexity:** Very simple and easy to build
- Circuit performance:** Very stable +5V output voltage, reliable operation
- Availability of components:** Easy to get, uses only very common basic components
- Power supply voltage:** Unregulated DC 8-18V power supply
- Power supply current:** Needed output current + 5 mA
- Circuit protection:** Built-in overheating protection shuts down output when regulator IC gets too hot

Fig 4. Flowchart

Flowchart - Flowchart of working of the project which is programmed in the Embedded C programming language in the Kiel µvision2. The system hardware was setup was connected to loads programs using the Flash Magic software

VI. RESULTS

Fig 5. Project in power supply 'ON'

Fig 6. PIR sensor

Fig 7. SMS sent

Fig 5. When the power supply is switched on the LCD will display the message “AUTOMATIC HOME SECURITY SYSTEM” and all the sensors are in ON mode.

Fig 6. When the PIR sensor detects any motion of human or animal, the LCD will display the alert and the GSM Module will send the alert message through SMS. (the message sent is displayed in LCD Fig 7)

Fig 8. Smoke or Gas detection

Fig 9. Fire sensor

Fig 10. Fire sensor detection display

Fig 8. When the smoke or gas is detected by the system, an alert message is displayed in LCD and the GSM Module will send the alert message through SMS. Also the exhaust fan which is implemented using the DC motor is switched on.

Fig 9 and Fig 10. When the Fire sensor detects any fire, the LCD will display the alert and GSM Module will send the alert message through SMS.

Fig 11. Duplicate key

Fig 12. SMS alert in cellphone

Fig 11. When a duplicate key is detected in the door lock, the LCD will display the alert and GSM Module will send the alert message through SMS.

Fig 12. The above picture shows the SMS alerts through GSM module is received in the mobile phone

VII. CONCLUSION

The hardware and software programming of the project was done successfully without any errors. In remote home security system, all the sensors are detected by the microcontroller and necessary alerts and fans are working successfully in the system. The advantages of this system it protects valuable items at home, it's a remote application, its sends fast alerts, it's very flexible type of system which can be implemented in any location and its cheap in cost cause the whole system is implemented using a single microcontroller. These system can be implemented in application like can be used in home, factories, chemical plants (can be used for gas leakage or fire detection), hotels (can be used for gas leakage or fire detection), ATM or banks (PIR motion can provide safety during night times), etc.

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